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Developing an instrument to monitor educational quality culture The Quality Assurance Barometer

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ABSTRACT

Quality assurance (QA) is experiencing a paradigm shift worldwide. The traditional emphasis on stakeholder satisfaction and compliance to external frameworks is increasingly being replaced or supplemented by a fundamentally different outlook, where institutional ownership, engagement to take responsibility for quality management, and trust are key [1,2]. Internal reflection is gaining importance, involving stakeholders such as management and lecturers. In this context the construct of quality culture is gaining importance. Monitoring whether a healthy quality climate is in place implies identifying and measuring different parameters such as perceptions, practices, attitudes, needs and ideas [3,4,5,6]. As a consequence, higher education institutions (HEIs) are faced with the challenge to develop new formats and tools for QA, and are looking for good practices.

This paper reflects on the Quality Assurance Barometer developed in 2018 by the multi-campus Faculty of Engineering Technology at KU Leuven university. The instrument was approached as an anonymous online survey. Its questionnaire was based on scientific literature on QA as well as input by faculty advisory boards. It measures attitudes towards QA in general, attitudes towards specific tools and practices, perceived impact of tools and structures, stakeholder needs, perceived priorities and opinions on potential new initiatives.

The barometer was filled in by n=167 academic staff members. Statistical analysis yielded useful feedback to strategic and middle management. Interestingly, some aspects of quality culture do correlate with other variables such as staff seniority and campus context. By sharing insights on the development of a quality culture monitoring tool, this paper may encourage other HEIs as well to take QA to the next level.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Faculty of Engineering Technology of KU Leuven is a multi-campus faculty organising (Bio)Engineering Technology programmes at seven campuses in Flanders,

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Belgium. As an entity the faculty comprises about 600 staff members and close to 6,000 students.

The faculty introduced its quality assurance barometer in 2018 for two reasons:

1. Internal process optimisation. Since its establishment five years earlier the faculty had implemented a wide scale of QA tools. The time was ripe to review current practices and to let staff signal needs and suggestions related to QA.
2. External reporting. A new QA decree in 2015 had allowed the HEI to transition from external program evaluations to institutional reviews. This evolution has made internal monitoring highly relevant as faculties are expected to take more responsibility for QA and to report periodically to central services as well as external peers on their QA system. Stakeholder feedback provides useful information to assess the faculty's processes and climate as well as to check whether existing tools are fit for this new context.

2 QUALITY ASSURANCE AND QUALITY CULTURE

2.1 Trends in quality assurance

Quality assurance (QA), in essence, is a means to provide reliable information to stakeholders so as to allow optimal decision-making [8]. Quality is and will remain a culturally sensitive and relative concept [1] with criteria which moreover depend on the stakeholder's own perspective [7]. Perspectives on quality and quality assurance moreover change over time.

In the 1990s, quality was mostly considered as fitness for purpose or value for money [6]. In most countries, QA was introduced as a way to deal with growing concerns about the quality of higher education in response to expanding student numbers, rising awareness on dropout rates, and demands for accountability about public spending. As a result, higher education institutions (HEIs) increasingly had to demonstrate compliance with (minimum) standards, provide transparent information, and build trust. Many QA models from the start had features in common [2]. In past decades QA could typically be equated to quality control by means of structured action guidelines (e.g. DIN EN ISO 9000/9001 standards) or continuous quality development approaches (e.g. Total Quality Management) [3].

Later on, quality was in some contexts redefined, for example as a search for excellence [6]. Changes in QA follow in response to new insights, critique and changes in contexts [2,9]. Current trends include a growing consideration for self-improvement, taking into account institutional diversity, and stronger stakeholder involvement. Many agencies are indeed opting for lighter, formative procedures in favour of HEIs' own responsibility for QA [1,9,10]. Understanding of QA is moreover being extended to include informal and non-structural aspects of quality as well [3,5]. In this context, assessing quality by means of hard facts no longer suffices. Discerning the extent to which values are subscribed to and lived by members of the HEI becomes at least equally relevant [4]. As a result the concept of quality culture is gaining importance.

2.2 The quality culture concept

The exact meaning of quality culture (QC) is subject to debate as it is a complex social-constructivist phenomenon [5,6]. Still, the definition originating from the European University Association (EUA)'s network meetings is generally accepted [3,4,5,6]:

“Quality culture refers to an organizational culture that intends to enhance quality permanently and is characterised by two distinct elements: on the

one hand, a cultural/psychological element of shared values, beliefs, expectations and commitment towards quality and, on the other hand, a structural/managerial element with defined processes that enhance quality and aim at coordinating individual efforts.” [1 p. 10].

Quality culture is often considered the answer to challenges, while in reality, its strength is to help identify challenges. QC monitoring is first and foremost a means to ask questions about how institutions function and how they see themselves [6]. Follow-up of results should likewise differ fundamentally from traditional approaches. The culturally sensitive and relative construct of quality means there are no intrinsically right or wrong answers, on the contrary: diversity in perspectives is in fact desirable as a starting point for dialogue, as this stimulates internal QC [1].

Recent years have shown growing appreciation for the QC concept. Yet there are a limited number of empirical studies on its operationalisation [3,5]. Moreover, those that can be found focus on the point of view of students and not as much on academic staff [3].

2.3 Quality culture frameworks

The following three frameworks illustrate different perspectives on QC.

The framework stemming from the heiQUALITY Cultures Project was specifically designed to explore and operationalise the concept in the higher education setting [3,4].

The EUA definition was its main inspiration. This model correspondingly describes QC as consisting of two interrelated components (*Fig. 1*): a structural-formal one (comprising normative, strategic and operative aspects, i.e. goals, principles, responsibilities, tools and measures) and an organisational-psychological one (individual and collective dimensions, i.e. commitment, sense of responsibility, engagement, leadership, communication, participation, shared values and trust).

The framework was subsequently translated into the Quality Culture Inventory, an umbrella term grouping two questionnaires: a structural-formal questionnaire to assess an organisation’s QA and quality management, and a survey on the organisational-psychological component [3,4].

Fig. 1. Assessment model of quality culture [3 p. 49].

A second model reflects on the interconnectedness of context, working mechanisms and outcomes as depicted in *Fig. 2* [5]. According to these authors, subcultures play a major role in individual and collective behaviour. Top-down and bottom-up approaches need to be balanced for quality management efforts to succeed. The structural-managerial and cultural-psychological elements must therefore be linked through elements such as leadership and communication [5].

Fig. 2. Context-mechanism-outcome-configuration of quality culture in HEI [5 p. 51].

A third way to look at QC is by means of ideal-types. A framework based on Cultural Theory considers individual behaviour as determined by the degree of group-control and the intensity of external rules [6]. The four ideal-types in *Table 1* are each affiliated with different QA systems and quality cultures. These ideal-types give insight in how tacit ways of dealing with issues should be taken into account when designing and analysing a QA system.

Whereas a responsive culture will proclaim an improvement agenda stressing accountability and compliance, it will be characterised by very low ownership and stakeholder control and be unconnected to everyday experience; yet stakeholders will react to external threats as a group. Reactive quality cultures are equally driven by compliance and accountability, but regard QC as something which is managed or imposed and therefore delegate it to a specific space such as a quality office. Regenerative quality cultures include external opportunities in so far as these are expected to provide learning opportunities or benchmarking possibilities; but will otherwise suppress external QA to the margins or actively subvert it, in a sense equating QC to everyday work practice. Reproductive quality cultures finally minimise the impact of external factors and focus on reproducing the status quo; in these contexts one refrains from open self-reflection and transparent QA practices as these are likely to result in resistance [6].

Table 1. Quality cultures in Cultural Theory framework, inspired on literature by Thompson et al. and Hood [6 p. 436].

Degree of group-control Intensity of external rules	Strong	Weak
Strong	Responsive	Reactive
Weak	Regenerative	Reproductive

A common feature in these frameworks is to emphasize the match between structure and culture, and how managerial and psychological dimensions are inherently connected. A multitude of dimensions interact and influence whether initiatives are successfully implemented. This makes defining and operationalising QC exactly so challenging: strictly isolating the concept is inadvisable. Monitoring QC moreover deals with both the individual and aggregate level. This implies that monitoring QC will necessitate including a variety of QA aspects in a broad sense, with regard to attitudes as well as processes, and to stay responsive to contextual influences all the while. The fact that quality culture is bound to values and expectations, besides, means that social desirability might bias results depending on the methodological approach.

3 MONITORING QUALITY CULTURE

The remainder of this paper will focus on a quality culture monitoring instrument developed in the context of an engineering faculty. The instrument was conceived as an addition to more traditional tools already in use. Its aims were both internal process optimisation and external reporting as is described in the introduction.

3.1 Questionnaire

In the past, external QA in Flanders applied content-related indicators, emphasizing compliance with standards and accountability. Internal QA would likewise focus on similar constructs. Institutional reviews on the other hand now adopt a systemic quality management perspective. The focus has in other words shifted from inputs and outputs to processes [2,9]. The developed tool had to follow suit in the same fashion.

Questionnaire items were chosen to fit with the dual goal of internal optimisation and external reporting, combining structural-managerial elements and organisational-psychological elements as advised by literature [1,3,4,5,6]. These elements were not divided as such though. Clustering questions thematically was more intuitive and reflective of daily practices of the target group, i.e. the faculty's staff involved in education. The survey covered the following sections and corresponding number of questions:

1. Attitudes towards QA in general (5 items)
2. Attitudes towards specific QA tools and practices (12 items)
3. Perceived impact of tools and structures (8 items)
4. Stakeholder needs, perceived priorities and opinions on potential new initiatives (8 items)

The questionnaire was based on scientific literature as well as input by faculty advisory boards. Items were discussed and validated by the faculty's advisory boards of experts on quality assurance, curriculum development and educational policy prior to the administration of the survey.

The questionnaire was concise so as to avoid response dropout. In contrast to literature [3,4], therefore, unique measures were preferred over multi-item scales. Examples of questions and corresponding response scales are included in *Table 2*. Each section included an optional text box where participants could clarify answers or add remarks. As it was the first time the barometer was conducted, this way stakeholders could also signal ambiguities, allowing to improve the questionnaire for future use.

Table 2. Sample items of the quality assurance barometer.

Section	Sample items	Response options or scale
1. Attitudes towards QA in general	I regard quality assurance primarily as the responsibility of...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Each individual lecturer - The teaching team - The programme coordinator - The programme director - The campus vice chair of education - The campus chair - The vice dean of education - The dean - Other: ...
	Which definition of “quality” fits best with your concept thereof?	Definitions obtained from literature [6]. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality as exceptional - Quality as perfection or consistency - Quality as fitness for purpose - Quality as value for money - Quality as transformation
2. Attitudes towards specific QA tools and practices	To what extent do you agree with the following statements? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback from students is instructive for me as a lecturer. - Student evaluations of teaching are relevant for HR decisions. 	6-point Likert scale ranging from “fully disagree” to “fully agree”.
	To what extent do you use the following as a lecturer? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback from the student evaluation of teaching - Peer review by colleagues 	5-point scale: never – rarely – sometimes – often – systematically
3. Perceived impact of tools and structures	In your opinion, which of these have the strongest impact on the quality of education in the faculty? (select at most 5 items)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Programme committee meetings - The student evaluation of teaching - Focus groups - Surveys conducted by the lecturer - Study time measurements - Professional field surveys - Alumni surveys - Personal contacts between lecturers - Personal contacts between lecturers-students - Peer review between lecturers - The faculty’s teacher team days - The former self-evaluation reports and programme evaluations - The institutional review - Other: ...

4. Stakeholder needs, perceived priorities and opinions on potential new initiatives	According to you, which aspect of quality assurance should get highest priority in the faculty?	Based on the formal protocol for institutional reviews: - Clarify vision and policy - Design processes, structures and instruments - Monitor processes and collect feedback - Encourage reflection on possible improvements
	According to you, which topics regarding quality assurance should the faculty address as a priority?	<Open question.>

Finally, demographic variables (campus, number of years of staff seniority) as well as potentially dependent or moderating variables (types of instructional activities staff engage in) were collected for statistical analysis of results.

3.2 Method

The instrument was approached as an online survey. This allowed for swift feedback by many respondents and conditional survey pathways. Participation was anonymous so as to avoid social desirability bias. As the faculty has an educational offer in Dutch as well as in English, the survey was available in both languages.

All staff members were invited to fill in the survey in May 2018. They were encouraged to do so by means of an announcement during a meeting of the Faculty Council with its 200 members, by email sent by the faculty’s vice dean of education to staff email distribution lists, and by one email reminder. Around 400 academic staff members are involved in the educational activities of this faculty; the barometer was filled in by n=167 respondents.

3.3 Lessons learned

As this concept paper deals in specific with the methodological aspect of developing a monitoring tool, the following paragraphs will share lessons learned and reflect on which measures or contrasts proved interesting to include in this type of monitoring survey, in retrospect from the point of view of the faculty’s QA team. Readers interested in the empirical report instead are invited to contact the author.

Each section of the questionnaire provided useful insights in its own way.

Attitudes towards QA in general allowed to get an overall idea to what extent staff members recognise responsibilities for QA. Even though healthy QA is a shared responsibility, the sample question in *Table 2* deliberately forced participants to pick one answer so as to be able to contrast the general climate to official policy. Also interestingly, the question measuring which definition best describes respondents’ personal vision on quality returned two values as the most popular: on the one hand fitness for purpose, the dominant perspective in the former program evaluations; on the other hand quality as transformation, which has better alignment with the institution’s current vision on education and teaching. Similarly, this section included a number of statements on the added value or burden of QA to educational development. Detailed analyses and open comments showed that staff seniority had an impact on responses: colleagues who had been around at the time of the former programme evaluations evaluated QA more frequently as a burden than less experienced colleagues did, giving testimony to the ghosts of the past of former external QA protocols.

Attitudes towards specific QA instruments bear witness to the support for and adoption of different tools and practices by staff members in their everyday activities. Campus and staff seniority were important contrasting variables here as subcultures deal with daily routines in different ways. Some campuses for example had a stronger tradition of informal meetings than others, and moderately experienced colleagues attached higher importance to formal meetings than their juniors and seniors did. Another interesting observation were the consistently positive correlations between several instruments or practices (e.g. surveys, peer review, good practices for curriculum development), giving evidence to the fact that adoption of these tools in daily practice was not a case of either-or but that proponents of one tool were in fact more likely to combine multiple tools. The open text box allowed respondents to share ideas on potential improvements or provided explanations on why certain items were more popular than others.

The perceived impact of tools and structures provides relevant information on which practices might prove crucial to reaching goals, and which might have become obsolete or need reorganisation. Here as well it is advisable to compare answers to formal policy decisions so as to evaluate whether stakeholder perceptions match with management's strategic choices, expectations and future plans.

Stakeholder needs, perceived priorities and opinions on potential new initiatives finally proved useful to confirm support for strategic decisions or to confront policy with blind spots. The recommendations provided through the open question generated useful input for advisory boards and policy actors. In the current context there were no significant differences between answers of subgroups as defined by background variables, allowing to define follow-up without need for differentiation.

4 DISCUSSION

The transition to a new QA context with stronger emphasis on institutional autonomy as well as the emergence of the concept of quality culture call for a different quality monitoring approach. This led to the development of a quality assurance barometer, described in this concept paper.

4.1 Reflection and conclusions

Monitoring whether a healthy quality climate is in place implies identifying and measuring different parameters such as perceptions, practices, attitudes, needs and ideas [3,4,5,6]. This evolution is also reflected in the QA barometer questionnaire described in this paper, as is illustrated by the sample items and lessons learned. The developed instrument indeed combines structural-managerial and organisational-psychological elements from several frameworks. By developing this instrument the faculty highlights quality culture as a relevant monitoring subject.

Follow-up related to the barometer mostly entailed contrasting results to current policy, which provided useful feedback and recommendations to management. Literature indeed suggests grounding the monitoring of quality culture in institutional strategy as the HEI's ambitions and values provide a shared framework for reflection [1]. When and if responses obtained through the barometer deviated from expectations, this was not by default interpreted as a problem to be remedied top-down; it rather provided a bottom-up stimulus for reflection and dialogue, aiding management and staff to stay in touch.

Including demographic, dependent and moderating variables in the questionnaire as well makes sure resulting interventions can be tailored to the expectations and needs of subcultures [5]. Literature also suggests ways of reporting on differences between subcultures, e.g. by visualising them as different profiles [4]. Differences between subcultures were minor in the current case study, yet did help in interpretation of results and gave insight in ghosts of the past.

4.2 Strengths, limitations and directions for future research

Quality culture is gaining relevance in the domain, evidenced by the fact that other entities in the faculty's environment are also becoming more aware of its significance. The university's central services for example are exploring how to translate the quality culture concept into general QA guidelines, and the external QA agency NVAO is paying increasing attention to this in protocols for e.g. initial program accreditation. The type of instrument described in this paper may prove valuable as an innovation and thereby provide inspiration for future developments.

The questionnaire itself may be optimized further. Some dimensions recently identified in literature were not yet included to their full extent, such as leadership and trust. Using unique measures instead of multi-item scales likewise limits the scope and validity of constructs to a certain degree. The instrument and its results were, nevertheless, appreciated by the relevant stakeholders and were able to provide useful insights as well as a baseline for future monitoring. Even if it is only feasible to include a limited array of questions, monitoring remains of added value.

A potential catch is that QA instruments can only succeed as long as the relevant stakeholders are willing to provide fair input and are convinced their answers will be taken seriously [4]. Stakeholder support was achieved by generating awareness about the purpose and process through both oral and written communication, and by keeping the survey anonymous. The fact that the barometer was a faculty initiative instead of being imposed by external drivers also facilitated stakeholder support. The response rate and usability of the answers seem to confirm the reliability and validity of the responses, in any case.

The instrument discussed in this paper will not automatically be transferable to other contexts. Indicators on quality culture do not provide absolute measures; analysis requires contextual interpretation and weighting [1]. Tools and processes should take into account their purpose and available resources, and will therefore differ depending on the context [7]. With regard to the barometer, getting a sound fit was achieved by having relevant stakeholders and experts validate the questionnaire and survey methodology before administration. The sample items and lessons learned may nevertheless provide inspiration to other HEIs as there is still limited literature on the operationalisation of quality culture [3].

Future efforts could relate to translating questionnaire results into follow-up initiatives, and to integrating the quality culture construct further into overall quality assurance systems. Literature provides some hints on when quality culture monitoring may prove useful and on how to report results to stakeholders [4], and stresses that subsequent interventions should be tailored to the context [5,7]. Yet there is still much to learn on how to effectively nurture a quality culture [5].

REFERENCES

- [1] European University Association (2006), Quality Culture in European Universities: A bottom-up approach. Report on the three rounds of the quality culture project 2002–2006. Brussels: EUA.
- [2] Vermeersch, J. (2018). External program evaluations and institutional reviews. A comparative overview and case study. *Proc. of the 46rd Annual SEFI Conference*. Copenhagen, Denmark: SEFI.
- [3] Sattler, C., Sonntag, K. & Götzen, K. (2016), The Quality Culture Inventory (QCI): An Instrument Assessing Quality-Related Aspects of Work, *In B. Deml et al. (Eds.), Advances in Ergonomic Design of Systems, Products and Processes* (pp. 43-56). Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.
- [4] Sattler, C. & Sonntag, K. (2018), Chapter 9: Quality Cultures in Higher Education Institutions - Development of the Quality Culture Inventory, *In Meusburger, P. et al (Eds.), Geographies of the University* (pp. 313-327), Knowledge and Space 12.
- [5] Bendermacher, G. W. G., oude Egbrink, M. G. A. O., Wolfhagen, I. H. A. P., & Dolmans, D. H. J. M. (2017), Unravelling quality culture in higher education: a realist review, *Higher Education*, 73(1), 39-60.
- [6] Harvey, L. & Stensaker, B. (2008), Quality culture: understandings, boundaries and linkages, *European Journal of Education*, 43(4), pp. 427-442.
- [7] Martin, M. (Ed.) (2018), Internal Quality Assurance: Enhancing higher education quality and graduate employability. Paris: Unesco Publishing, International Institute for Educational Planning. Retrieved from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0026/002613/261356E.pdf>.
- [8] Blackmur, D. (2004), Issues in higher education quality assurance, *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 63(2), pp. 105-116.
- [9] Wächter, B., Kelo, M., Lam, Q.K.H., Effertz, P., Jost, C. & Kottowski, S. (2015), *University Quality Indicators: A Critical Assessment*, Brussels: European Parliament, Committee on Culture and Education, pp. 23-47 and 75-76.
- [10] Billing, D. (2004), International comparisons and trends in external quality assurance of higher education: Commonality or diversity?, *Higher Education*, 47(1), pp. 113-137.